

Family Engagement in Reading for Pleasure with Young Children in the Seychellois Home. What Does it Look Like?

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Introduction

Reading is a fundamental part of a child’s development, shaping language skills, imagination, and emotional growth from an early age. Sharing books with young children not only sparks a lifelong love of reading, but also creates joyful moments of connection, dialogue, and bonding between children and their caregivers. In the early years, reading is more than just words on a page – it is a playful, engaging, and deeply nurturing activity. In Seychelles, understanding and supporting positive reading habits at home can play a vital role in every child’s learning journey.

This article reports on introductory work done in understanding reading habits in Seychelles under the project ‘*Sesel Lir avek Mwan*’ (SLAM). SLAM is a national, community-based parental support project launched by the Seychelles Association of Retired Education Professionals (SAREP) in 2023 to raise awareness of the importance of reading with children from an early age, and to empower parents and family members to engage in literacy activities at home to support their children’s cognitive, emotional and social development. To approach these goals, it was first necessary to gain a better understanding of the current state of reading habits in Seychellois homes.

In this pursuit, SAREP teamed up with the Education and Socio-Economic Research Institute (ESERI) of the University of Seychelles to conduct a baseline Home Literacy Survey (HLS) on reading habits. The purpose of the survey was to gather data on the reading practices, literacy environment and beliefs about reading of a target group of parents in Seychelles to gain a better understanding of the home literacy situation in order to plan future support interventions.

This paper reports on the findings of the HLS and the insights gathered from introductory workshops with parents in districts and workplaces. Although largely based on self-reported responses, and a relatively small sample of participants, we would argue that it provides an overview picture of the reading context in Seychellois homes.

Previous Research

In recent decades, there has been a growing interest in research in early *Reading for Pleasure* (RfP) especially in the UK and New Zealand, where RfP appears in policy documents and is mandated in the national curriculum. RfP has been described by the International Literacy Association (2018) as the opportunity to read freely, voluntarily, and with delight in anticipation of some form of satisfaction. While there is no scientific definition of RfP, the concept has been used by different researchers to describe any kind of non-obligatory reading that the reader gets pleasure from (Boyask et al., 2021; Clark and De Zoysa, 2012; Clark and Rumbold, 2006).

Proponents of the RfP movement highlight the importance of encouraging RfP in young children during the critical early childhood stage, as RfP has been associated with beneficial outcomes for cognition and mental health later in life. For example, a large-scale study by Sun et al., (2024) on the attainments of early childhood RfP, found that such activities were positively associated with cognitive benefits and negatively associated with dimensional psychiatric problems in young adolescents. In her review of research on RfP, Cremin (2019) concluded that reading recreationally in childhood and beyond brings about cognitive, social and emotional benefits. Cremin (2019) thus argues that equal importance be given to children's recreational reading as to reading for decoding and comprehension.

A large number of international studies, both quantitative and qualitative, document the concrete multiple benefits of reading for children – see for example Beck and McKeown, 2001; Doak, 2024; Schoppmann et al., 2023. BookTrust (2023), one of UK's largest children's charity organizations, summarizes these benefits under four headings in a recent publication entitled *Reading Together, Changing Children's Lives*. According to this report, children who read and participate in shared reading are more likely to: 1) overcome disadvantages caused by inequalities; 2) be happier, healthier and experience better mental wellbeing and self-esteem; 3) do better at school and make more progress across the curriculum; and 4) develop empathy and creativity. (BookTrust, 2023).

In relation to very young children, research findings have also shown that when adults share picture books with babies and children, there are both immediate and long-term benefits such as physical closeness and shared attention, enjoyment and interaction (Betawi, 2015; Hale et al., 2011; O'Farrelly et al., 2018). An evaluation of a National Literacy Trust early years programme by Wood et al. (2015) also found significant benefits of sharing books, in particular the impact that reading has on the quality of children's home learning environment.

Studies advocating the importance of shared reading make reference not only to shared reading at a very young age, but also the frequency of reading and the number of books

available in the home (Hoyne and Egan, 2019; Roulstone et al., 2011; Swalender and Taube, 2007). Such studies also note that benefits are also associated with other adults – grandparents, guardians or older siblings – reading regularly to a child. A positive attitude towards reading is also an important aspect to be considered. Findings from a number of studies show that parents’ attitudes, values and beliefs about early literacy have a direct impact on the entire family’s attitudes to reading (Hoyne and Egan, 2019; Roulstone et al., 2011; Swalender and Taube, 2007). We have included questions that relate to several of these aspects in the Home Literacy Survey.

While the positive benefits of reading to young children thus seem to be well established, research on strategies to engage parents and children to read is scarcer. Two initiatives launched in the UK looked into gifting books for babies (Hardman and Jones, 1999; Moore and Wade, 2003). Both initiatives suggested benefits of gifting books to babies for reading and language experiences. However, these studies also emphasize the importance of extra support and guidance to parents on how to interact and read with their child. It thus seems that although availability of reading materials is important, more is needed. This is SLAM’s approach, which takes on the challenges of changing reading culture in Seychelles from several angles and in ways which actively involve primary stakeholders, including the parents. It is also in line with recent research which shows how participatory research and workshop activities can have great benefits in changing reading habits (see Webber et al., 2024).

In summary, reading for pleasure has been seen as one of the top three predictors of children’s reading performance as they enter formal schooling (Lindorff et al., 2023). However, we note gaps in research on reading for pleasure. For example, little work has been done on how to encourage such activities on a large scale. An understanding of the factors that encourage and support shared reading in early childhood is essential to foster a reading culture, and particularly important in underprivileged contexts. Nevertheless, we find that most research conducted so far on shared reading and reading for pleasure in early childhood have mainly been conducted in more developed countries. Similar studies in small island developing states, for example, are scarce if not non-existent. Hence the SLAM project in Seychelles is important, not only for our own contexts, but also to set an example of how small island developing states can work with this issue.

Method

Overview

The data that forms the basis of this article was gathered from introductory workshop meetings of the project *Sesel lir avek mwan* (SLAM). From June 2023 to September 2024, seventeen such introductory sensitization sessions for parents were held in various districts and workplaces on Mahé, the main island of Seychelles. These introductory sessions gave

SAREP facilitators the opportunity to interact with 224 parents/caregivers of children aged 0-5. During these sessions, we also asked our participants to fill in a Home Literacy Survey (HLS), an online survey on reading habits. Of the 224 participants who attended the sessions, 167 completed the HLS.

Each sensitization session lasted between two and a half to three hours starting with an introduction, completing the HLS, and an ice-breaking exercise. Topics covered included information on early brain development, the importance of talking and listening to children for vocabulary and language development; tips on expanding vocabulary through everyday activities; and the benefits of reading aloud, sharing books, and making reading fun for children from very early ages. The sessions also exposed parents to a variety of books appropriate for different age groups and introduced ideas for making their homes more book and literacy 'friendly'.

A wide variety of methods was used to inform and engage the participants, including power point presentations, short videos, group discussions, reading-related icebreakers and inspirational material. Good practices in interactive reading and storytelling for development of vocabulary and creativity were modelled with the active participation of the parents and children whenever they were present.

The sessions were conducted in a relaxed, friendly, inclusive, and non-judgmental setting and participants could share experiences and challenges. Notes of discussions and brainstorming sessions were recorded on flip-chart paper and later analysed and validated by facilitators. There was, however, no systematic recording or detailed coding of the qualitative data gathered during these sessions as we felt that this would have interfered with the central activity. The qualitative insights (observations and comments) gained from the sessions thus complement the quantitative data gathered from the survey and serve to give a fuller picture of the home literacy environment, attitudes to reading, and lifestyles of parents in Seychelles.

The Home Literacy Survey

The survey was produced using the online survey tool, SurveyMonkey, which allowed for easy distribution digitally via a link, or via a QR-code (for smart phone usage). SurveyMonkey also allowed for print-out formats in Pdf. The languages used in the survey were English and Kreol Seselwa, and the answer to an initial language choice question led respondents to one or the other of these two alternatives.

Pilot versions of the survey were first designed by co-workers at the Education and Socio-Economic Research Institute (ESERI) of UniSey in close collaboration with key SAREP members. A pilot version of the survey was tested in field with relevant test groups, and feedback from these sessions was then used to improve the comprehensibility of the survey.

The survey was distributed at various SLAM workshops held from June 2023-September 2024. All respondents were informed about the purpose of the survey and that the information received would be used for an article on reading habits. The informants were free to opt out of taking the survey, and the survey also contained a question where informants were asked to confirm that the information could be used for a study on reading habits. Also note that all the surveys were completely anonymous with no i.p. address information recorded. Approximately 60% of the respondents chose to answer the online version of the survey and 40% filled in paper versions. The results from these paper versions were fed into the survey databank. A total of 167 respondents answered the survey. Of these 68 chose the English and 99 the Kreol Seselwa version. Results below will be in English. Any free text responses will be indicated as translations where relevant.

Survey format

The survey consisted of a total of 35 questions (ten pages) with primarily different closed multiple choice type questions: one answer option multiple choice questions; multiple answer option multiple choice questions; slider responses whereby respondents could use a slider to indicate to what degree (%) a statement was accurate in describing their situation; seven-point Likert scale statements where 1 = ‘Totally disagree’, 4 = ‘Neither agree nor disagree’, and 7 = ‘Agree completely’, and free text comment options. The survey was designed to capture various types of information related to reading. Topics are summarized in Table 1 below:

Table 1: Survey content

Themes	Details asked for
Demographics of the respondents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◇ Relationship to child ◇ Gender ◇ Age ◇ District ◇ Nationality ◇ Occupation ◇ Education
Household structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◇ Number of adults ◇ Number of children ◇ Number of pre-school children ◇ Childcare solutions
Reading materials – types and availability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◇ Types of printed materials ◇ Quantity of printed materials ◇ Accessibility of printed materials

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◇ Types of digital tools/materials ◇ Quantity of digital materials ◇ Accessibility of digital materials ◇ Where parents/caretakers get the literacy resources from
Reading habits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◇ Who reads with the children ◇ Time of day reading takes place ◇ How often adults read for the children (frequency) ◇ Time spent reading per week
Language	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◇ What languages are used when reading ◇ What languages are used when talking about the text ◇ What languages are spoken in the home
Views on reading	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◇ Does the child read? ◇ Enjoyment ◇ Importance of reading as a life skill ◇ Who is responsible for ensuring children's literacy skills ◇ Knowledge about child development ◇ Literacy culture in the home
Other aspects	Free text answers

Demographics of respondents

Most of the respondents were female (87.6%) and only 12.4% were male. No respondent defined themselves as 'Other'. The majority of the respondents (86%) who attended the workshops were parents, and of these 78% were mothers. Legal guardians constituted only 4% of the sample, but nevertheless this group is of special interest since all the legal guardians included in the survey were childcare workers working in children's homes. This gave us insights into the literacy environments in these institutions. An overview of the respondents' relationship to the target group children is given below in Figure 1.

Figure 1 : Respondent relationship to the child / children targeted by the project (i.e. young children 5 years and below)

As regards the age of the respondents, it is noteworthy that a relatively large proportion of the respondents were very young parents of 25 or below (30%). The largest group constituted parents in the 19–25-year span. The different age groups from 26-45 were relatively evenly distributed. The age group 55+ was primarily made up of respondents who were grandparents to the children. The results are summarized in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Respondent age groups

The socio-economic groupings were based on the International Standard Classifications of Occupations (ISCO-8).¹

¹<https://ilostat.ilo.org/methods/concepts-and-definitions/classification-occupation/>

To make this data meaningful for any type of analysis (i.e. so that the sub-groups do not become too small), we have joined sub-groupings to create three socio-economic categories only: Group 1, consisting of ISCO Categories 1 and 2 (managers and qualified professionals); Group 2, consisting of ISCO Categories 3, 4, 5 and 6 (see descriptions in Table 2 below); Group 3: Category ‘Other’ consisting of ISCO Category 9 and ‘Other’, which were generally unemployed. The distribution of the respondents according to these groupings is summarized below. Also note that these socio-economic groupings (1-3) will be used in any cross-tabular analysis of the results below.

Table 2: Socio-economic groups and categories

Groups	ISCO-categories	ISCO-category distribution	Group distribution
Group 1	Category 1: Managers	11.8%	32.7%
	Category 2: Qualified professionals	20.9%	
Group 2	Category 3: Associate professionals	5.5%	31.8%
	Category 4: Clerical support work	16.4%	
	Category 5: Service and Sales	7.3%	
	Category 6: Skilled agricultural	2.7%	
Group 3	Category 9: Elementary occupations, unskilled manual workers, unemployed etc.		35.5%

In the questionnaire, seven different options for highest level of finished education were given: primary education; obligatory secondary education; non-obligatory secondary education; post-secondary tertiary education (professional programmes); university bachelor level; university master level; and university doctorate level. No respondents chose primary or doctorate level options. Furthermore, we decided to merge the two secondary school options and the bachelor and master level options to create fewer categories for meaningful analysis. The distributions of the respondents based on education categories is given in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Education levels of respondents

Highest finished level of education	Respondent distribution
Secondary school	33%
Tertiary professional programmes	52.2%
University education	14.8%

Results

Quantitative HLS results

Household structures and day care solutions

A surprisingly large proportion of the respondents live in households with more than two adults present (63%). Only 31.9% of the respondents in the survey lived in households with two adults present, and very small proportion (5.1%) were single parent households.

The most common number of children aged five and below per household was one child (71%). Only 5% of the households had three or more children aged five years and below. The results are summarized in Figures 3 and 4 below.

Figure 3: Adults per household

Figure 4: Target group children (0-5) per household

Most households have more than three adults and the relatively high adult:young child ratio in the Seychelles households is something that could benefit reading culture if more adults than the parents in the household are involved in establishing reading habits.

Also, most pre-school children in this survey (72%) attended daycare centres outside the home. Approximately 20% were cared for in the homes either by parents or relatives and a small proportion (8%) attended Creche. It is thus apparent that daycare centres are also primary potential collaborative partners that can contribute to the SLAM project.

Reading resources in the homes

The available printed literacy resources for pre-school children in the homes of the respondents is dominated by picture books (available in 79.4% of the homes). Story books are also popular (76.3%). Furthermore, there are various resources listed in the survey such as cartoon magazines, games with text, flash cards and posters, but these are less popular, available in approximately 30-40% of the homes. Overall respondents indicated that they had modest amounts of printed materials in their homes (some books and one or two games etc). More specifically, the score on the sliding scale question which ranged from 0% (none at all) to 100% (an abundance of resources) was 47%. Also worth noting was that 8.2% of the homes lacked printed literacy resources.

Digital hardware literacy resources for pre-school children in the homes of the respondents was dominated by the television, available in 84.6% of the homes. Smart phones were also popular (66%). Other resources listed in the survey include tablet devices (47.4%), computers (12.4%), TV-game consoles (8.2%) and video recorders (8.2%). Overall, respondents indicated that they had modest amounts of digital resources in their homes (TV and some games). More specifically, the score on the sliding scale question which ranged from 0% (none at all) to 100% (an abundance of resources) was 50%. Note that

6.3% of the homes lacked digital literacy resources. In hindsight, a weakness of our survey was the fact that we did not ask specifically how the different digital resources were used. The results for printed and digital resources are summarized in Table 4 below.

Table 4: Reading resources in homes of respondents

Printed resources	Availability in % respondent homes	Digital tools/hardware?	Availability in % respondent homes
Picture books	79.4%	Smart Phone	66.0%
Story books	76.3%	Tablet device	47.4%
Cartoon magazines	30.9%	Computer	12.4%
Games with text	41.2%	Television	84.5%
Flash cards	33.0%	TV-game console	8.2%
Posters with text	40.2%	Video recorder	8.2%
Estimated quantity in home	modest (47%)	Estimated quantity in home	modest (50%)

We also asked respondents about the accessibility of the various resources from the child’s perspective. Alternatives here included: ‘Fully accessible’ (i.e. books are displayed where children play and at a level where they can reach them); ‘Displayed visibly’ (i.e. kept in a place where children can see the resources but not reach them, and thereby available on request); ‘kept safe away from vision’ (i.e. kept in cupboards and drawers and brought out when adults decide to do so); ‘No resources’ available.

Overall, printed resources were much more accessible to children than digital resources. Most of the respondents kept books etc. in places freely available to the child with no restrictions. Digital resources were a lot more restricted with only 25% of the respondents keeping these in a way that was fully accessible to children. In many ways, this is predictable as digital hardware is often expensive and easily damaged, something which speaks for printed materials being more suitable for smaller children.

The final part of this section in the HLS asked where parents and caregivers got their literary resources from. Results show that the majority of respondents bought their reading materials in shops. Getting books and other resources as gifts was another important source. However, only 10.4% of the respondents used libraries as a source of reading materials. Results are summarized in Figure 5 below.

Where do you get your reading resources from?

Figure 5: Sources of reading materials

Reading habits – Who reads?

Mothers read to their children in 83.3% of the homes in the survey. Fathers do so in approximately 26% of the homes. It was also interesting to note that grandparents are relatively active in reading to children (28%). Note that the percentages add up to more than 100% since respondents could choose one or more answer options. Results are summarised in Figure 6 below.

Figure 6: Persons reading for the child in the homes of the respondents

Reading habits – When, how often and for how long?

Most respondents (87%) indicated that they read to their children in the evenings. Overall, the frequency of reading and time spent reading to children was quite limited. Only 19.1% of the respondents read to their children daily. The vast majority only read to their children once or twice a week and 10% of our respondents rarely or never read for their children. (see ‘Total’ in Table 5 below).

Table 5: Frequency of reading different respondent categories

Category	Sub-categories	Every day	At least once a week	At least once a month	Rarely/never
Highest Education level	Secondary school	18%	46.4%	25%	10.7%
	Tertiary professional	18.8%	58.3%	14.6%	8.3%
	University education	23.1%	61.5%	0%	15.4%
Socio-economic grouping	1	23.1%	50%	11.5%	15.4%
	2	22.6%	61.3%	12.9%	3.2%
	3	14.8%	59.3%	11.1%	14.8%
Age category parents only	15-18 years	16%	58%	13%	13%
	26-35 years	22%	53%	19%	6%
	36-50 years	33%	50%	14%	3%
Total overall	Mean all	19.1%	55.1%	15.7%	10.1%

Looking at the different social categories, the following tendencies emerge in the frequency data in Table 5. Education level seems to be a relatively uncertain predictor of how often caregivers read to their children. There is a very slight tendency for university educated caregivers to read more frequently than the other groups, but this does not constitute a significant difference. Furthermore, there is a slight tendency for social category 3 to read less frequently to their children, but again, this is not a very significant trend. The age of caregivers is a better predictor of frequency of reading. There seems to be stronger tendencies for older parents to read to their children more frequently than younger parents. For example, only 16% of the younger parents read to their children every day whereas the same figure for the older parents was 33%.

In relation to time spent reading to the child, the overall trend was that caregivers spent relatively little time a week reading to their children. Over 70% spent less than half an hour

a week on this activity and only 14% read to their children more than one hour a week (see ‘Total’ in Table 6 below). Looking at the different social categories, university educated respondents stood out (see Table 6 below). A relatively large proportion of university educated parents (30.8%) spent more than an hour a week reading to their children. Only 15.4% of university educated parents spent less than ten minutes reading to their children; the equivalent figures for the other parent education categories were more than 39%. The differences in time spent reading between the different socio-economic groups were marginal, with only a slight tendency for social category 3 to read less than the other two groups. Finally, there was a strong tendency for older parents to spend more time reading to their children than younger parents. For a summary of the results for time spent reading, see Table 6 below.

Table 6: Time spent reading a week

Category	Sub-categories	Less than 10 minutes a week	10-30 minutes a week	30 mins – 1 hour a week	More than 1 hour
Highest Education level	Secondary school	39.3%	28.6%	21.4%	10.7%
	Tertiary professional	39.6%	37.5%	10.4%	12.5%
	University education	15.4%	53.8%	0%	30.8%
Socio-economic grouping	1	38.5%	38.5%	3.8%	19.2%
	2	29%	38.7%	19.4%	12.9%
	3	48.1%	33.3%	3.7%	14.8%
Age category parents only	15-18 years	55%	30%	12%	3%
	26-35 years	28%	53%	11%	8%
	36-50 years	22%	42%	11%	25%
Total overall	Mean all	36%	37.1%	12.4%	14%

Language habits

Kreol Seselwa and English were the dominant languages in the survey. Kreol Seselwa was by far the most common language used in the home for everyday conversation (93%), which was also reflected in the language used to talk about texts when reading; 83% use Kreol Seselwa for this purpose. The most common language for reading, however, was English (81%), which may reflect limited availability of texts in Kreol Seselwa suited for young children. It may also be the case that parents prefer to read English texts to prepare children for school. Kreol Seselwa was, however, also a popular reading language in the

survey with 72% of the respondents reading Kreol Seselwa texts for their children. Reading in French was marginal. Note that respondents could choose one or more options, which explains the percentages adding up to more than 100%. The results from the language section of the HLS are summarized below in Table 7.

Table 7: Language habits

Activities	Languages			
	Kreol Seselwa	English	French	Other, N/A
Everyday language at home	93%	60%	3%	2%
Language for reading	72%	81%	8%	4%
Language to talk about text	83%	68%	4%	3%

Children’s reading ability

The majority of children referred to in the survey could not read at all (62%) or only recognized the odd word (29%). A small percentage could read simple sentences (5%) and 4% were referred to as fluent readers.

Views on reading

The results of this section were based on responses to various statements related to different aspects of reading. Respondents could agree/disagree with these statements based on a 1-7 Likert scale where low figures (1 = Minimum) indicated disagreement with the statements and high figures (7= Maximum) signalled agreement. The neutral response ‘Neither agree nor disagree’ was represented by the value 4.

Greatest agreement in our results was with the statement ‘I believe reading is an essential life skill’, with a mean score value of 6.4. Respondents also tended to agree with the statement ‘It is my responsibility as a parent to develop my child’s reading habits’. Here the mean score was 6.2. Most respondents also agreed with the statement ‘I really enjoy reading with my child!’ (mean score 5.7). The two statements ‘In our home, we read regularly and talk about what we read in a way that the child can see and relate to’ and ‘I have a good understanding of early brain development in children and appropriate literacy activities for each age group’ were met with modest agreements on average (5.2 and 5.4 respectively). The statement that parents had most disparate opinions about was ‘It is the responsibility of the school to develop my child’s reading habits’. Here the mean score was 4 indicating that respondents neither agreed nor disagreed. The responses to the various statements included in the survey are summarized below in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Responses to various statements

The exercise also provided the facilitators with a better understanding of the needs of young families and how they can be best supported to promote early literacy and a love for books and reading at home prior to school entry. It also provided pointers for additional research areas.

Free text answers

Finally, various opinions were expressed in the free text comment answers. Most comments simply confirmed the general findings from the survey, for example that respondents believed that it was the parents who had primary responsibility for their children’s literacy development:

Learning starts at home and schools are for supports.

We need to encourage more parents to start reading with their children at home and thereafter the daycares and school will do their part.

It is the responsibility of every adult to help their child in life.

[free translation from Kreol Seselwa]

Other respondents took the opportunity to express frustration at how difficult it was to find the time to read with their children due to aspects such as traffic:

My current work schedule is 8 to 5pm, and after spending 1 hour in traffic and getting home at 6.30pm the little time left to spend with my kids before bedtime mostly involves talking about my kids day and spending some one-on-one time whilst winding the kid down for bedtime.

Qualitative findings

The findings below summarise our observations and discussions with parents and caretakers.

Parents' expectations for their children

The large majority of parents who attended the sessions on a voluntary basis had high expectations for their children. They wanted their children to succeed at school and have good jobs. They wished their children to grow up with good moral values and '*savoir vivre*', to respect others and live in harmony in the community. The majority recognized the importance of reading competency for success at school and for gaining new knowledge. Only one group, young teenage mothers, did not have any expectations for their children or were unable to express them at this stage.

Although participants recognized the role of parents and the home in nurturing good reading habits, there was little recognition of the importance of developing habits of reading for pleasure for emotional wellbeing or reading as a social activity. Many parents were primarily concerned with formal educational aspects such as teaching children how to decode words, to know the letters of the alphabet, to recognize colours and to know how to count in preparation for school. This was also reflected in the types of books they bought for their children. There were lone voices in each group who spoke of the pleasure of reading. It was also these parents who claimed they regularly bought books for their children and took them to the library.

The majority of parents stated that their children were not interested in reading. Watching cartoons on TV and tablets and playing games on the phone were preferred pastimes. Many parents spoke proudly of how cartoons and television series had improved their children's vocabulary and pronunciation.

Barriers to reading with children

The sessions were also an opportunity to explore the barriers preventing parents from reading more frequently with their children. The most commonly cited barrier was time restraints, an issue that was taken up frequently in discussions. Work and family commitments, transport problems and sometimes coping with two jobs, left little time to read with children during the week. Listening to stories of the daily routines of mothers who worked long shifts in hotels or had to cope with two jobs corroborated the point made that finding time to read can be a big challenge for many parents. However, we would

argue that misconceptions about what reading is about in early years and that the focus should be on pleasure is an equally important hurdle that needs to be overcome (see discussion below).

Skills and knowledge on how to read with children

The sessions revealed that many parents lacked basic skills and know-how related to reading with children. They reported that attempts to read with their children frequently ended in frustration. They found children had 'poor attention span', that they would 'not focus', that the children were 'easily distracted' and started 'wandering around' in the middle of a story. Some children wanted to 'read the same book over and over again' and insisted on parents 'reading books to them when they were busy with other chores'. Some parents also expressed irritation at children turning pages, damaging the books, focussing on one picture only, or taking the lead in choosing what to read.

Demonstrations of shared reading to parents and showing videos on how to involve their children in conversations around a book, how to follow up on their children's expressed interests, and leading the reading were eye openers for many parents. Parents were surprised to see their children, who they claimed had no interest in reading, engaging positively in shared reading delivered by facilitators.

We also observed that many parents lacked confidence and were shy when asked to role play, engage with books, or make funny noises and gestures to gain the children's interest. For many parents, the majority of participants, who had not experienced shared reading at home as children, this was a new experience.

In summary, guidance, and demonstrations of good practice in interactive reading from trusted professionals will be an efficient way to encourage parents to embed reading into their daily routine and make reading an enjoyable activity. Basic advice on how to create the conditions for reading at home (finding a quiet cosy corner, choosing the right moment, setting up a display of attractive books) can turn a stressful experience into an enjoyable one at home.

Availability and variety of age-appropriate books

Our conversations with parents corroborate the survey findings of moderate amounts of print and digital literacy resources being available in homes. High quality modern children's books of various genres that can stimulate reading for pleasure are costly and not easily accessible in local shops, which are the primary source of books among the project participants. Parents were also unfamiliar with what books to buy and different genres, including comics and graphic books. Discussions also showed that choices of books were highly gendered: popular books for girls were stories about princesses and for boys about transport. It was interesting to observe children spontaneously interacting with the variety of books we had displayed during the sessions and follow their own interests.

Particularly popular were interactive books containing features such as sliders, mirrors and flaps to stimulate their curiosity.

We note from the survey findings that 81% of parents read to their children in English but 83% revert to Kreol Seselwa to talk about the story. We were not able to establish whether parents read in English because of the unavailability of books in Kreol Seselwa, or if they did so to provide early exposure to English, the main language of instruction in schools.

Discussion

Firstly it is important to note some of the limitations of this study. The small size of the group of respondents means that the results cannot be generalized to the Seychelles population of parents/caregivers with confidence. Furthermore, because the respondents were people who had been interested enough to attend the workshops in the first place, we cannot maintain that this is a random sample.

With these limitations in mind, our results show that the reading culture in Seychelles is relatively limited. With few exceptions, reading on a daily basis with young children is not part of the daily routine in most Seychelles families. Although there are some greater tendencies for certain social groupings (older and well-educated parents in particular) to prioritize reading to their children, the fact remains that fewer than one in five of Seychelles parents and caregivers read to their children on a daily basis, and over 70% of parents and caregivers spend less than 30 minutes a week reading to their children. There may be several reasons for this.

From conversations and discussions in the workshops, we found that most parents read to their children, not for pleasure, but rather as a learning activity to prepare their children for school. This attitude was arguably mirrored in the HLS where most parents saw it as their responsibility to develop their children's reading habits. The danger with this view is that reading becomes another chore that has to be fitted into what is already a fully crammed schedule of routines and obligations. The idea of reading for pleasure, just for the fun of it, gets lost.

Given the above views on reading expressed by parents, i.e. that it is primarily an educational activity, it is hardly surprising that children seem to be disinterested in reading and find it difficult to concentrate. Just as might be the case for parents, young children may be associating reading with chores and would rather do something else.

If this is the case, it would follow that reading becomes unprioritized, especially given that it appears to be seen as the prime responsibility of women/mothers, a group which is already extremely overburdened with responsibilities. Here we see a need to engage fathers

and other household members to take a more active role in reading activities. Given the fact that most Seychellois households have more than three adults, it is reasonable that other adults, in addition to mothers, can benefit from the pleasures of reading with children.

We maintain that challenging these mindsets is the number one priority if we want to introduce a reading culture in the Seychelles. The principles of reading for pleasure, an activity that can be carried out by any caring adult be they male or female, should be highlighted, and methods for how this can be done should be showcased. For example, book readings using engaging language, gestures and prompts could be included in daycare activities and also televised as part of the local children's programmes. These types of role model examples need to be presented to parents, and here institutions such as daycare centres, libraries and public media can play active roles.

Access to reading materials is another area that should be prioritized, and here we would argue that the need for quality children's books in Kreol Seselwa is a key priority. Although picture books in any language can be used, true engagement and immersion in the story is dependent on culturally relevant stories where children can mirror themselves and their families in environments and cultural contexts that they recognize. It is no surprise to note that 83% of parents revert to Kreol Seselwa to talk about the book as deep connections and bonding over shared experiences occur more naturally through the use of the mother tongue. Currently books for young children written in Kreol Seselwa are very limited and this is another priority area.

Finally, from our findings it appears that digital resources are being prioritized over printed books. This may partly be a result of books being expensive and the fact that libraries are not used habitually. More studies are required on how children engage with digital resources and the quality and appropriateness of digital resources that are available in the homes for literacy development. Although there are increasingly louder voices that caution on the dangers of excessive exposure to screen at a very early age (Mansouri et al., 2022), good quality digital resources used judiciously and with the interaction of adults can ignite children's desire to read especially in multilingual contexts and in homes where good quality printed books are rare.

Summary and conclusion

To conclude, Reading for Pleasure is not well understood, practiced or promoted by the majority of parents in the study. The number of parents/families who read with children on a daily basis is very low and the home literacy environment is poor with a moderate number of books or digital resources available. Parents who read with their children do so primarily for instrumental educational reasons rather than for enjoyment or to instil a love

of reading in children from a very early age. Those who do read regularly with children seem to be overwhelmingly concerned with teaching them the mechanics of reading, to know their letters and sounds, to be able to know numbers, to count, and to distinguish colours to be prepared for school. This is also reflected in the variety and types of books that they purchase for their children.

Our observations and interactions with parents also confirm that the majority have not experienced reading for pleasure at home as children and lack the skills and support to promote it. Their knowledge of contemporary children's books is also limited as evidenced in ice-breaking exercises where a vast majority could not mention the title or author of one children's book.

Current parenting programmes do not provide guidance on cognitive development and reading for pleasure and there are limited opportunities for families to meet and share experiences of reading with children in informal settings. There are also very few parental resources to support literacy development and guidance for parents on contemporary children's literature.

It is important thus that all partners and service providers working with children aged 0-5 – including bookshop owners, librarians, daycare workers, educators, media producers etc. – work together to promote reading for pleasure and include literacy development in their practice. It is also necessary to review the importance and place given to reading for pleasure in all early years' curriculum. In effect, we need to introduce a culture where we start enjoying books *with* our children, rather than seeing books as instruments of education.

This is where the SLAM project can be helpful. It aims to address many of the issues discussed above: a) changing a poor culture of reading for pleasure in Seychellois homes; b) counteracting parents' lack of awareness on how to promote early language and literacy; and c) counteracting the limited access to age-appropriate and literacy materials in Kreol Seselwa for young children in the home.

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